

Benefits and Socio-economic Impact with the Adoption of Bhavantar Bharpai Yojna (BBY) in Haryana

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The present study examines the adoption of Bhavantar Bharpai Yojana (BBY) among beneficiary farmers in Haryana, with special reference to Fatehabad district. BBY is a price deficiency payment scheme aimed at protecting farmers from distress sales arising due to fluctuations in market prices below the government-declared base price. A descriptive and analytical research design was adopted, and primary data were collected from seventy BBY beneficiary farmers selected through purposive sampling. Data were gathered using a structured interview schedule and analyzed using frequency, percentage, chi-square test, weighted mean score, and rank order analysis. The findings revealed that the majority of farmers exhibited a medium level of adoption of BBY. Secured crop price, increased income, and protection against low market prices emerged as the major reasons for adoption. The scheme was perceived as beneficial in ensuring an assured income and reducing price risk. However, delays in payment, limited crop coverage, and procedural issues were identified as major constraints. The study highlights the role of BBY in improving farmers' income stability while emphasizing the need for timely payments and wider coverage.

Keywords: Bhavantar Bharpai Yojana (BBY), adoption, reasons for adoption, benefits

Agriculture continues to be the primary source of livelihood for a large proportion of India's population, particularly in rural areas. Although the country has achieved self-sufficiency in food production, farmers often face severe price declines at the time of harvest, which adversely affect their income and economic stability. Bhavantar Bharpai Yojana (BBY) was first introduced by the Government of Madhya Pradesh on October 16, 2017, as a price deficiency payment scheme aimed at protecting farmers from distress sales caused by fluctuations in market prices (Anynomus, 2017). Recognising its potential, the Government of Haryana adopted the scheme in 2018 to safeguard farmers' incomes when market prices fall below the Minimum Support Price (MSP) or the government-declared base price. Under BBY, when the market price of a notified crop is lower than the predetermined "Bhavantar" price, the price difference is directly transferred to registered farmers (IIM, 2018). This mechanism ensures that farmers receive fair compensation for their produce even during periods of unfavourable market conditions.

Initially, the scheme focused on selected horticultural crops such as tomato, onion, potato, and cauliflower, as these crops are highly perishable and prone to sharp price fluctuations due to seasonal gluts. Over time, BBY was expanded to include additional crops based on market volatility and farmers' needs, with the broader objective of encouraging crop diversification into vegetables, fruits, and millets that are not covered under conventional MSP procurement systems. At present, the scheme covers 21 horticultural crops, including five fruit crops, fourteen vegetable crops, and two spice crops (Government of Haryana, 2018).

Price formation from the producer to the consumer is influenced by complex demand supply interactions involving multiple intermediaries operating at different levels of the agricultural marketing system. Marketing structures and institutional arrangements significantly affect price realisation at various stages, from the farm gate to the final consumer. In India, nearly forty types of vegetables belonging to different groups are cultivated, with crops such as potato, tomato, onion, cabbage, and cauliflower accounting for nearly 60 per cent of the total vegetable production. In Haryana, vegetables are grown over an area of about 447 thousand hectares and contribute approximately 3.9 per cent to the country's total vegetable production (Anonymous, 2022).

Despite this substantial contribution, farmers in Haryana frequently face the problem of price crashes at the time of harvest, particularly for perishable vegetable crops (Chand, 2017). Awareness among vegetable growers in Haryana was also reported to be only about 46%, and 60% of respondents were unaware of registration procedures, claim mechanisms, and contact details for support (Bhaker et al., 2020). Even though most farmers agreed that BBY could reduce income risks, they also believed the current process is too complicated, especially for those with limited education or digital skills (Bhaker et al., 2020). Such challenges are not new. Earlier studies have consistently shown that factors such as education level, size of landholding, access to extension services, and participation in farmer organisations play a crucial role in

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determining farmers' awareness of government schemes and their ability to benefit from them (Kumar et al., 2021; Awasthi & Mishra, 2019). In states like Haryana, where levels of literacy and digital access vary considerably, these factors often lead to significant information gaps among farming communities (Gaurav & Mishra, 2012). Knowledge is also one of the challenges in the implementation of BBY. About one-sixth of the respondents (15.83%) had a low level of knowledge. Approximately one-third of the respondents (44.17%) had a medium level of knowledge. The remaining respondents, making up two-fifths (40.00%), demonstrated a high level of knowledge (Athpalia et al., 2025). Moreover, the increasing reliance on digital platforms for scheme registration, such as *Meri Fasal Mera Byora*, has added another layer of complexity. While such systems aim to improve transparency and efficiency, they can unintentionally exclude farmers who lack digital literacy or access to technology, thereby limiting the reach of otherwise well-intentioned schemes (Mittal & Mehar, 2016). In this context, it becomes essential to assess the actual knowledge levels of BBY beneficiaries, identify the socio-economic factors influencing their awareness, and understand the practical constraints they face while availing benefits under the scheme.

Therefore, to improve the overall implementation and socio-economic impact of BBY in the state, as well as to help formulate more effective strategies, the current study was conducted with the following objectives-

Objectives of the Study

- To find out the reasons and adoption level of Bhavantar Bharpai Yojana among farmers.
- To study the benefits of Bhavantar Bharpai Yojana.
- To know the socio-economic impact of Bhavantar Bharpai Yojana on farming families
- To assess the constraints of Bhavantar Bharpai Yojana

Method

The present study was conducted to examine the adoption of Bhavantar Bharpai Yojana (BBY) among beneficiary farmers, along with the associated benefits, socio-economic impact, and constraints faced in its implementation. A descriptive and analytical research design was adopted, as it was considered appropriate for assessing farmers' adoption behaviour and related socio-economic dimensions under an ongoing government scheme.

Participants

The research was carried out in Fatehabad district of Haryana state, which has substantial participation under the Bhavantar Bharpai Yojana. Two blocks, namely Fatehabad and Bhuna, were purposively selected due to the higher concentration of BBY beneficiary farmers. From Fatehabad block, the villages Bhuthan Kalan, Jhalania, and Badopal were selected, while Bhuna, Gorakhpur, Chandrawal, and Jandli Khurd villages were selected from Bhuna block. A total of seventy (70) male beneficiary farmers registered under Bhavantar Bharpai Yojana were selected as respondents for the study in the age group of 20 years to 65 years. The respondents were selected using a purposive sampling technique, ensuring that only those farmers who had availed benefits under the scheme were included. This helped in obtaining reliable

and relevant information in accordance with the objectives of the study.

Procedure

Primary data were collected through the survey method using a well-structured interview schedule. The interview schedule was prepared based on the objectives of the study and included information related to socio-economic characteristics, reasons for adoption, level of adoption, perceived benefits, socio-economic impact, and constraints in the adoption of BBY. Data were collected through personal interviews, which facilitated better understanding and accuracy of responses.

Measure

Measurement of Adoption Level: The adoption level of farmers regarding Bhavantar Bharpai Yojana was measured using a composite adoption score based on responses to selected adoption statements. Based on the total score obtained, respondents were categorized into low, medium, and high adoption levels using appropriate class intervals.

Measurement of Benefits, Socio-economic Impact, and Constraints: Perceived benefits and constraints related to BBY were measured using a three-point continuum (Agree, Neutral, Disagree). The socio-economic impact of the scheme on farming families was assessed using response categories such as Increase, Somewhat Increase, and No Change across different socio-economic indicators.

Statistical Analysis

The collected data were coded, tabulated, and analyzed using suitable statistical tools. Frequency and percentage analysis were used to describe respondent characteristics and adoption levels. The Chi-square test was applied to examine associations between selected socio-economic variables and the adoption level. Weighted mean scores and rank order analysis were used to prioritize reasons, benefits, and constraints related to Bhavantar Bharpai Yojana.

Results

Reasons for the Adoption of Bhavantar Bharpai Yojana (BBY)

The data in Table 1 indicate that the primary reason for the adoption of BBY was the secured price for crops, with 77.14 per cent of respondents agreeing. This was followed by increased income (60.00%) and a reduction in the low prices of crops in the market (55.71%). Other notable reasons included year-round income generation for different crops if adopted (51.43%), programme intensification (50.00%), and fair sale of produce on J-form (47.14%). Fewer respondents agreed with reasons such as improved farm satisfaction (45.71%), easy access to BBY information (42.86%), and portal ease (31.43%). More than 50 per cent of respondents had awareness regarding the implementing agency, its objectives, the crops included under the scheme, and the eligibility of farmers under the scheme. But most of the respondents (more than 60 %) were not aware of the registration process, area verification, sale period, or procedure of claiming benefit under BBY.

Table 1*Reasons for Adoption of BBY (n=70)*

Statements	Agree (3)	Neutral (2)	Disagree (1)
Adopted to secure prices for the crops.	54 (77.14)	10 (14.29)	6 (8.57)
Adopted due to the increase in the income of farmers	42 (60.00)	20 (28.57)	8 (11.43)
Adopted due to the reduction of low prices in the market	39 (55.71)	21 (30.00)	10 (14.29)
Adopted due to income-generating activity round the year	36 (51.43)	25 (35.71)	9 (12.86)
Adopted due to the intensification of the programme	35 (50.00)	27 (38.57)	8 (11.43)
Adopted due to sale of produce on J-form on daily basis/seasonal basis	33 (47.14)	29 (41.43)	8 (11.43)
Adopted due to satisfaction after registering for this scheme	32 (45.71)	27 (38.58)	11 (15.71)
Adopted due to easy access to information about BBY	30 (42.86)	29 (41.43)	11 (15.71)
Adopted due to easy process on portal	22 (31.43)	23 (32.86)	25 (35.71)

Note. Figures in Parentheses indicate percentage, Responses were multiple

Adoption Level of the Farmers Regarding Bhavantar Bharpai Yojna (BBY)

The following Table 2 presents the farmers' adoption level regarding BBY. In terms of adoption level, the maximum of respondents (44.29%) fell into the medium category, followed by 35.71 per cent with low adoption and 20.00 per cent with high adoption.

Table 2*Adoption Level of Farmers Regarding BBY (n=70)*

Adoption level	Frequency	Percentage
Low (9-14)	25	35.71
Medium (15-21)	31	44.29
High (22-27)	14	20.00

Benefits of Bhavantar Bharpai Yojana (BBY)

Table 3 highlights perceived socio-economic benefits of the Bhavantar Bharpai Yojana (BBY) among farmers. A majority (72.86%) agreed that BBY is a boon for growing farmers, giving it Rank I with the highest weighted mean score (2.68). This was

followed by its role in reducing market price loss risks (57.14%), ranked II (2.42), and providing assured income (48.57%), ranked III (2.34). Inclusion of bajra was agreed upon by 42.86 per cent of respondents, earning Rank IV (2.18). The scheme's impact on expanding cultivation area and its benefits for farmers on leased/shared land received lower agreement levels, 35.71 per cent and 30.00 per cent respectively, placing them at Rank V (2.05) and VI (2.01).

Figure 1*Adoption Level of Farmers Regarding BBY***Table 3***Benefits of Bhavantar Bharpai Yojana (BBY) (n = 70)*

Benefits of BBY	Agree (3)	Somewhat agree (2)	Disagree (1)	TWS	WMS	Rank
Bhavantar Bharpai Yojana is favourable for farmers	51 (72.86)	16 (22.86)	3 (4.28)	188	2.68	I
It reduces the risk of farmers suffering losses due to low market prices	40 (57.14)	20 (28.57)	10 (14.29)	170	2.42	II
Assured income for the farmer	34 (48.57)	26 (37.14)	10 (14.29)	164	2.34	III
Millets (Bajra) are included in this scheme	30 (42.86)	23 (32.86)	17 (24.28)	153	2.18	IV
BBY Triggers farmers to expand area under bajra and other crops	25 (35.71)	24 (34.29)	21 (30.00)	144	2.05	V
BBY is beneficial for farmers who cultivate on leased or shared basis	21 (30.00)	29 (41.43)	20 (28.57)	141	2.01	VI

Note. Figures in Parentheses indicate percentage

Cumulative Socio-economic Impact of BBY on Farming Families

The socio-economic impact shows (Table 4) that the most noticeable improvement was in investment on quality education of children, which 48.57 per cent which was reported some increase. This was followed by a somewhat increase in social participation (45.71%) and agricultural land on lease (44.28%). For most indicators, a

significant number of respondents reported no change, particularly in the purchase of household assets (62.85%), social status (65.71%), and extension contacts (57.14%). Aspects with relatively somewhat increases reported were income (37.14%) and decision-making powers (28.57%), indicating that while there were some positive effects, the overall impact varied across different socio-economic dimensions.

Table 4*Cumulative Socio-economic Impact of BBY on Farming Families (n = 70)*

Socio-economic Impact Parameters	Increase	Somewhat Increase	No change
Participation in Social activities	10 (14.29)	32 (45.71)	28 (40.00)
Expenditure on the performance of social ceremonies like marriage, death, etc.	7 (10.00)	30 (42.85)	33 (47.14)
Income	8 (11.43)	26 (37.14)	36 (51.43)
Extension contacts	7 (10.00)	23 (32.86)	40 (57.14)
Purchase of household assets	5 (7.15)	21 (30.00)	44 (62.85)
Increase in social status	4 (5.71)	20 (28.57)	46 (65.71)
quality of medical treatment	8 (12.70)	27 (42.86)	35 (44.44)
Improvement in Good decision-making powers.	9 (12.86)	20 (28.57)	41 (58.57)
Investment on quality education of children	3 (4.28)	34 (48.57)	33 (47.14)
Agricultural land on lease	11 (15.72)	31 (44.28)	28 (40.00)

Note. Figures in Parentheses indicate percentage, Responses were multiple

Figure 2*Cumulative Socio-economic Impact of BBY on Farming Families***Table 5***Constraints in Adoption of BBY (n=70)*

Constraints	Agree (3)	Neutral (2)	Disagree (1)	TWS	WMS	Rank
Beneficial only for a few crops (not for horticultural crops)	21 (30.00)	25 (35.71)	24 (34.29)	137	1.95	II
Problem in getting benefit under the scheme due to wrong registration of khewat or khasra number/ kila number on the registration portal	20 (28.57)	22 (31.43)	28 (40.00)	132	1.88	III
Delay in payment and implementation of the scheme	35 (50.00)	21 (30.00)	14 (20.00)	182	2.6	I
The sale of produce on J-Form on a daily basis/crop basis makes BBY cumbersome	20 (28.57)	20 (28.57)	30 (42.86)	130	1.85	IV

Figures in parentheses denote percentage.

Note. Responses were multiple

Also, a substantial portion agreed that difficulties in benefiting from the scheme due to incorrect registration of land details on the portal present a significant obstacle, suggesting issues with the registration process. Kathpalia et al. (2025) reported in a study conducted in Mahendergarh and Bhiwani district of Haryana that a significant majority agreed that delays and problems in the implementation of the BBY scheme pose a major constraint, indicating frustrations with administrative inefficiencies. Secondly, a substantial portion agreed that difficulties in benefiting from the scheme due to incorrect registration of land details on the portal present a significant obstacle, suggesting issues with the registration process.

Summary

It is summarized that the study was conducted to analyze the

Constraints in the Adoption of BBYs

Table 5 outlines key constraints faced by farmers under the Bhavantar Bharpai Yojana. The most reported issue was the delay in getting payment (Rank I), with a weighted mean score (WMS) of 2.60. This was followed by actual benefits for a few crops only, like bajra but not for horticultural crops (vegetables & fruits), noted by 30.00 per cent of respondents, ranked II (WMS 1.95). Incorrect registration of khewat/ khasra/ kila numbers was cited as a constraint by 28.57 per cent of farmers, placing it at Rank III (WMS 1.88). Lastly, 28.57 per cent agreed that the requirement to sell produce on a J-Form basis makes the scheme cumbersome, earning it Rank IV with the lowest WMS of 1.85.

adoption level, perceived benefits, socio-economic impact, and constraints of Bhavantar Bharpai Yojana (BBY) among farmers in Fatehabad district of Haryana. BBY was introduced to safeguard farmers against market price volatility by compensating the difference between the market price and the government-declared base price. The study covered 70 beneficiary farmers selected from two blocks, namely Fatehabad and Bhuna. Data were collected through personal interviews using a well-structured interview schedule and analyzed with appropriate statistical tools.

The results indicated that 44.29 per cent of respondents had a medium level of adoption, followed by low and high adoption categories. Secured pricing for crops, increased income, and reduction in market price losses were the primary reasons for adopting the scheme. Farmers perceived BBY as favourable due to

its role in ensuring an assured income and reducing financial risk, particularly for crops vulnerable to price fluctuations. The socio-economic impact showed moderate improvements in education expenditure, social participation, income, and decision-making ability, while several indicators, such as household assets and social status, remained largely unchanged. Major constraints reported included delays in payment, limited crop coverage, and procedural complexities such as J-Form requirements. Overall, the study concludes that BBY is a supportive income-stabilization scheme, but improvements in implementation and coverage are essential for enhancing its effectiveness.

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